

Outputs in UoA28, History, K. Sayer

We have found that output formats in History are typically: authored books (i.e. 'monographs'), chapters in and/or authorship of peer-reviewed edited collections, and journal articles. Searching the literature, there is little discussion of alternative outputs in History as a discipline, though Panel D guidance for the last REF2020/21 was wide ranging.¹ There do not seem to be many articles published on this issue in the discipline, which is more likely to discuss sources, or the trends in published research. Discussion about the use of potential alternative routes to dissemination of research tends to come via blogs from universities, researchers and organisations: trade books, text books, policy briefs, public lectures, documentary film & TV, websites, exhibitions, art installations and performances, digital resources e.g. online exhibitions, timelines etc., podcasts and blogs.² Co-authoring is also considered a new aspect of history publishing, with emerging discussions e.g. use of CREDIT.³ This is interlinked with emerging 'diversity' in UoA28, i.e. in a positive research culture diverse outputs are recognised alongside/as part of the broader recognition for diverse historical skills (e.g. public engagement), experiences across career stages, diverse research themes, and inclusive practices re EDI. However, our research using the REF20/21 data demonstrates that there seems to be a tendency to write about alternative outputs, rather than to produce actual alternative outputs in UoA28.

We drilled down into History in the REF as a comparative case of a discursive discipline, comparable culturally to Business. UoA28 in REF21 involved 81 submissions, with 5,766 outputs submitted.

¹ See [ref-2019_02-panel-criteria-and-working-methods.docx](#)

² Johnson, Oliver. "Alternative Histories of Soviet Visual Culture." *Kritika: Explorations in Russian and Eurasian History* 11, no. 3 (2010): 581-608. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1353/kri.0.0166>; Brennan C. Digital humanities, digital methods, digital history, and digital outputs: History writing and the digital revolution. *History Compass*. 2018; 16:e12492. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hic3.12492>; NB publication studies is its own sub-discipline e.g. Lerg, Charlotte A., Östling, Johan and Weiß, Jana. *History of Intellectual Culture 2/2023: Modes of Publication*, Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783111078038>; Gustafsson, L., Haapoja, T., & Museum of the History of Cattle, host institution. (2020). *History According to Cattle* (T. Haapoja & L. Gustafsson, Eds.; First edition.). punctum books. Brownlow, G., Cox, C., & McLaughlin, E. (2024). Irish Economic and Social History, 1974–2023: Publication Trends. *Irish Economic and Social History*, 51(1), 9–17. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03324893241277700>; see also [Publishing your work | RHS ECH Publishing: Other Formats | RHS](#); [7 Digital Tools That Help Bring History to Life | Edutopia](#); [Alternative Forms of Publication | Georgetown University Library](#); [Research Resources. Support for historians | Institute of Historical Research](#); [Home - History & Policy](#)

³ [CRediT – Contributor Role Taxonomy](#)

Q. what was the breakdown for types of output in history in the last REF?

Unit of assessment 28: History

Summary information

Number of submissions	81
Category A FTE staff submitted	2,360.21
Headcount of Category A staff submitted	2,472
Headcount of early career researchers	330
Number of outputs submitted	5,766
Number of outputs attributed to former staff	393
Number of case studies submitted	248

Research doctoral degrees awarded

2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	Total
503.39	550.43	565.66	563.77	582.07	534.27	524.30	3,823.89

Research income (£M)

2013-14	2014-15	Average annual income		Total 2013-14 to 2019-20
		2015-16 to 2019-20	2013-14 to 2019-20	
29.05	34.14	36.92	35.40	247.81

Research outputs

Number of outputs attributed	Category A submitted staff					
	All		ECR		Former staff	
	Headcount	%	Headcount	%	Headcount	%
1	884	36	168	51	79	37
2	770	31	106	32	105	49
3	410	17	39	12	19	9
4	281	11	10	3	8	4
5	119	5	5	2	3	1

'All' output types submitted in History, excluding A-D

Output type	n. submitted
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E – Conference contribution	8
H – Website content	5
M - Exhibition	1
N – Research report for external body	2
R – Scholarly edition	40
S – Research data sets and databases	6
T - Other	5
U – Working paper	8

Most of these are discursive (e.g. R, the largest here, is ‘scholarly edition’), with lower numbers submitted for the most potentially innovative and dynamic output types. Interestingly, websites/datasets, dramatic performances and films, which were in use in the discipline during the census period, were not submitted often as outputs, but seem more prevalent in Impact Case Studies.⁴

Business includes outputs of types: E(42), G(1), N(24), R(1), T(1), U(58), V (1). Most were ‘U’/‘E’/‘N’ i.e. discursive outputs, with 1 example of software.

2021 Research Excellence Framework Results										
Outputs										
Institution UKPRN code	Institution name	Main panel	Unit of assessment number	Unit of assessment name	Multiple submission letter	Multiple submission name	Joint submission	Output type	Title	Place
10007764	Heriot-Watt University	C	17	Business and Management Studies				G	PDSLASSO & LASSOPACK : Stata module for post-selection and post-regularization	
10007759	Aston University	C	17	Business and Management Studies				R	Regulation of Internet Pornography : Issues and Challenges	
10007768	The University of Lancaster	C	17	Business and Management Studies				V	The Worker : Dominion and Form	

Keyword searches

By comparison, considering the potential impact of the theme/subject of research on the choice of output type, searching for a keyword like ‘modern’ and then filtering output types (excluding A-D incl.) shows the variation across all UoAs that have the word ‘modern’ in a submitted output:

Output type (all UoAs)	n. submissions (all UoAs)
E	3
H	1
L	4
M	6
N	2

⁴ E.g. a keyword search on ‘slave’ produces 20 results, that include dramatic performances, exhibitions, databases and webpages etc.; whereas a search for ‘slave’ in UoA28 Outputs, excl A-D results in a single return, E a conference contribution.

R	10
T	13
U	2

Keyword search 'modern' across all UoAs, by output type, excl. A-D.

None of these outputs were from Business & Management Studies; and none were from History, though both UoAs are represented in the full set of outputs including A-D for the keyword.

Similar results, searching all disciplines, come with a search on 'social', which has 1 'R' output in History (filtering out A-D), and in Business includes four outputs types 'E', 'U' and 'N'.

We then searched for the following keywords, in outputs' titles in both UoA 17 and UoA28:

Exhibition
 Design - patent
 Visual design
 Toolkit
 Software
 Video/Film/Documentary
 Performance
 Game
 Website
 Dataset

Some adjustments had to be made for some terms, specific to the subject, as discussed below.

In UoA28, History, this produced the following results:

Search term	Standard outputs, A-D	Alt outputs, specified
Exhibition	4	1 - H
Design ['-patent' del.]	11	0
Visual design	0	0
Toolkit	0	0
Software	0	0
Video/Film/Documentary [excl. text sources]	1/18/2	0
Performance [i.e. street/dramatic/dance etc.]	14? ⁵	0
Game ⁶	2	
Website [c.f. 'exhibition'/H]	0	1 - S
Dataset/database	0/1	0/1 - S

The search was made more complex by some specialised uses of language e.g. 'documentary' can refer to 'documentary sources', as in text within history – excluded here – and 'performance' is sometimes used figuratively in the discipline. The latter usage was unclear, without always being able to access the output, so all uses have been entered in the table.

⁵ 'Performance' is often used figuratively

⁶ 'Game' is often used figuratively – an attempt has been made to exclude that usage

‘Game’ is mostly used to refer to actual historical games, e.g. the Olympics, cricket etc. or figuratively. Two outputs seemed to refer to the use of games in historical dissemination, though one OA link returns a 404 error.⁷ One return came from ‘website’, and the link still functions: [The Digital Panopticon](#) (last accessed, 20/06/25). Dataset and database show that UoA28 is more likely to use the latter term. One output is type S, which is still accessible [Welcome | The Cult of Saints 2019 Edition](#) (last accessed, 20/06/25). The term ‘website’ is ambiguous in the discipline/research assessment: it seems to have been returned either as ‘H’ or as ‘S’ in history, given the findings here. Another output returned as ‘D – journal article’ to Ref, encapsulated a large body of data and graphics [Historic ports and coastal sailing routes in England and Wales, 1540-1914 - ReShare](#) (last accessed, 20/06/25).

In most instances, the results returned showed an interest in discussing alternative ways of showcasing research, and the potential socio-cultural or political and economic issues arising from the subject of the research represented. But such studies normally written up in traditional output format.⁸

An additional problem is that something returned as website content (H) in February 2020, may no longer be accessible (in 2025), e.g.

Women in the Miners’ Strike, 1984-5. An essay to accompany the exhibition at the National Coal Mining Museum for England

Submitting institution	University College London
Unit of assessment	28 - History
Output identifier	13106
Type	H - Website content
Month	February
Year	2020
URL	http://www.ucl.ac.uk/women-miners-strike

Return as ‘Bad gateway’ on 20/06/2025

⁷ S. Poole, (2017). Ghosts in the Garden: locative gameplay and historical interpretation from below#. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 24(3), 300–314. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527258.2017.1347887>; Robert Houghton. (2018). World, Structure and Play: A Framework for Games as Historical Research Outputs, Tools, and Processes. *Práticas Da História*, 7, 11–43. <https://doi.org/10.48487/pdh.2018.n7.22437>

⁸ e.g. Benjamin Houston, Not as It Is Written: Blending Oral Histories and Historic Photographs in a Civil Rights Exhibition. *The Public Historian* 7 May 2020; 42 (2): 78–100. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1525/tpb.2020.42.2.78>

Bad gateway Error code 502

Visit cloudflare.com for more information.

2025-06-20 13:39:43 UTC

You
Browser
Working

Manchester
Cloudflare
Working

www.ucl.ac.uk
Host
Error

What happened?

The web server reported a bad gateway error.

What can I do?

Please try again in a few minutes.

Cloudflare Ray ID: 952bac02c1185ef0 • Your IP: [Click to reveal](#) • Performance & security by Cloudflare

Appendix a:

Datasets: UoA 28/History in REF21

[annex-k-output-glossary-and-collection-formats.pdf](#)

[ref-2019_02-panel-criteria-and-working-methods.docx](#)

[Unit of assessment 28: History : Results and submissions : REF 2021](#)

[Unit of assessment summary : Results and submissions : REF 2021;](#)

[Output profiles - REF 2021](#)

[Submissions data - REF 2021](#)

[Analysis of inclusion for submission, representation in outputs attribution and scoring - REF 2021](#)

<u>Select all</u>	<u>Select none</u>
<input type="checkbox"/>	A - Authored book
<input type="checkbox"/>	B - Edited book
<input type="checkbox"/>	C - Chapter in book
<input type="checkbox"/>	D - Journal article
<input type="checkbox"/>	E - Conference contribution
<input type="checkbox"/>	F - Patent/ published patent application
<input type="checkbox"/>	G - Software
<input type="checkbox"/>	H - Website content
<input type="checkbox"/>	I - Performance
<input type="checkbox"/>	J - Composition
<input type="checkbox"/>	K - Design
<input type="checkbox"/>	L - Artefact
<input type="checkbox"/>	M - Exhibition
<input type="checkbox"/>	N - Research report for external body
<input type="checkbox"/>	P - Devices and products
<input type="checkbox"/>	Q - Digital or visual media
<input type="checkbox"/>	R - Scholarly edition
<input type="checkbox"/>	S - Research data sets and databases
<input type="checkbox"/>	T - Other
<input type="checkbox"/>	U - Working paper
<input type="checkbox"/>	V - Translation